

HIGH THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY CARBON-CARBON COMPOSITES FOR THERMAL MANAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

A series of high thermal conductivity 2D laminate carbon-carbon composites were fabricated with mesophase derived pitch fibers as reinforcement in a graphitic carbon matrix. The bulk densities of balanced and unbalanced composites ranged from 1.80 to 2.10 kg/m³ x 10³. Thermal conductivities ranged from 125 W/m·K in the y direction to 500 W/m·K in the x direction of the fibers. Tensile strengths and moduli ranged from 210 to 380 MPa, 275 to 415 GPa and interlaminar shear strengths from 9 to 17 MPa in the x direction of the fibers. Innovative processing increased the matrix conductivity by a factor of up to 1.7 over baseline technology.

1. INTRODUCTION

High thermal conductivity materials are important in systems where high heat loads must be managed, i.e. transported or dissipated. High specific thermal conductivity is critical in many applications to minimize weight and volume. Recent development of continuous high thermal conductivity and high modulus mesophase derived pitch fibers, by Amoco Performance Products, Inc., which have a room temperature thermal conductivity of > 1100 W/m·K and a modulus of 895 GPa, has made it possible to design and fabricate continuous fiber carbon-carbon composites with high thermal conductivities and excellent mechanical properties. A carbon-carbon composite with a high specific conductivity combined with high strength and high modulus can serve as a structural component that also requires high thermal conductivity. The unique characteristics of these carbon-carbon composites make them attractive where thermal management improvement is critical to meet or exceed mission goals in spacecraft, aircraft, satellites, nuclear reactors, electronic packaging or chemical heat exchangers. High thermal conductivity carbon-carbon composites can be tailored during manufacture, within limits, by controlling fiber type, volume and direction to meet specific requirements.

2.0 MATERIALS

Composites were fabricated with mesophase derived pitch fibers developed by Amoco Performance Products, Inc. The fibers used in this program were an intermediate in Amoco's K-1100X fiber line with a modulus of 380 GPa. K-1100X fibers have a thermal conductivity of 1100 W/m·K and moduli of 895 GPa. Complex cloths and preforms may be easily woven with the 380 GPa fibers, whereas, such configurations are more difficult to weave with fully fired high moduli fibers.

Two dimensional cloth both balanced and unbalanced were woven with the 380 GPa fibers and used to fabricate 2D laminate composites. Carbon matrices were deposited from pitches and hydrocarbon gases. The aim of the process studies was to produce high in-plane thermal conductivity along with good mechanical properties in the composites.

3.0 EXPERIMENTAL DATA

Thermal and mechanical properties are presented in Tables 1 and 2, respectively.

3.1 Unbalanced 2D Composites

The 2D laminate composites fabricated with unbalanced cloth had bulk densities in the range 1.80 to 2.10 Kg/m³ × 10³, thermal conductivities in the range 425 to 500 W/m·K in the in-plane x direction and 125 to 260 W/m·K in the in-plane y direction.

The coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) was negative ranging from -0.4 to -0.1 ppm/C in the x and y directions, respectively.

Tensile strengths, moduli and interlaminar shear strengths measured in the x direction were in the range 210 to 380 MPa, 275 to 415 GPa and 9.6 to 17.2 MPa, respectively.

3.2 Balanced 2D Composites

The 2D laminate composites fabricated with balanced cloth had bulk densities in the range 1.85 to 2.00 Kg/m³ × 10³, thermal conductivities in the range 260 to 375 W/m·K in the x and y directions with x/y ratios in the range 0.90 to 1.02.

The coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) was negative ranging from -0.6 to -0.1 ppm/C in the x and y directions, respectively.

Tensile strengths, moduli and interlaminar shear strengths measured in the x direction were in the range 240 to 275 MPa, 210 to 275 GPa and 9.0 to 10.3 MPa, respectively.

Table 1. Thermal Properties of High Thermal Conductivity C/C Composites

PROCESS	BULK DENSITY (Kg/m ³ x10 ³)	THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY (W/m·K)		THERMAL EXPANSIVITY (ppm/C)	
		x	y	x	y
2D UNBALANCED CLOTH					
A1	1.96	479	154	-0.2	-0.2
A2	1.96	504	144	-0.3	-0.1
A3	1.81	429	129	-0.2	-0.2
B	1.88	447	127	-0.3	-0.1
C	2.08	425	--	--	--
D1	1.95	490	209	-0.4	-0.1
D2	1.93	508	262	-0.1	-0.1
2D BALANCED CLOTH					
A1	1.97	327	328	-0.3	-0.3
A2	1.92	317	319	-0.3	-0.3
A3	1.96	263	280	-0.2	-0.2
B	1.86	284	280	-0.3	-0.1
D1	1.93	336	370	-0.3	-0.2
D2	1.93	376	367	--	--

FIGURE 1. UNBALANCED 2D C/C COMPOSITES

FIGURE 2. BALANCED 2D C/C COMPOSITES

Table 2. Mechanical Properties of High Thermal Conductivity C/C Composites (x Direction)

PROCESS	BULK DENSITY (Kg/m ³ x10 ³)	TENSILE STRENGTH (MPa)	TENSILE MODULUS (GPa)	INTERLAMINAR SHEAR STRENGTH (MPa)
2D UNBALANCED CLOTH				
A1	1.96	379	393	17.2
A2	1.96	324	337	15.6
A3	1.81	317	445	13.6
B	1.88	221	324	10.1
C	2.08	276	290	14.0
2D BALANCED CLOTH				
A1	1.97	290	233	9.5
A2	1.92	283	228	9.2
A3	1.96	262	221	10.5
B	1.86	248	214	9.7

4.0 DISCUSSION

The thermal conductivities of the unbalanced and balanced composites in the direction of the fibers are plotted as a function of the composite bulk density in Figures 1 and 2, respectively. There is a correlation between bulk density and thermal conductivity in a given composite or preform architecture. The thermal conductivity of the composites fabricated by the D process was higher by a factor of 1.7 in the y direction and 1.1 in the x direction over of baseline processing. This increase is attributed to improved conductivity in the carbon matrix.

The C/C composites developed on this program combine high thermal conductivity with excellent mechanical properties. These composites should find application as components in thermal management systems where high thermal conductivity and strength are required where light weight and low volume are critical issues.

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